

A methodology of Using the Decomposition of Odd Pairs in Relation to Goldbach's Conjecture

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Abstract—We would like to suggest a new approach for the Goldbach conjecture. This is an unsolved problem that says that every even integer greater than 2 is equal to the sum of two prime numbers. By fragmenting the conjecture into smaller, provable components, we build up a logical framework through a combination of number-theory methods and the pigeonhole principle to connect the circulation of odd primes to the structure of even numbers. Our results may not provide a full proof of the Goldbach conjecture. Instead, they give our perspective on the combinatorial mechanisms underlying Goldbach-type decompositions and clarify the limitations that any probable proof must fulfill.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The conjecture was first announced by Goldbach in 1742, said that every even integer greater than 2 is equal to the sum of two prime numbers. [3] Mathematicians have tried to prove it by using different methods, from analytics to computational. However, a full proof of this problem has not yet been reached until now.

In this paper, we build a simple and easy to understand framework which is based on basic knowledge of number theory and the pigeonhole principle. Within 3 pages, it does not take long for the reviewer to read and comprehend our logic.

Our aim is not to offer a full proof of the conjecture. Instead, we suggest a potential method so that reviewers can enhance it to the perfect solution.

II. METHODOLOGY

First of all, I rewrite the conjecture as follows

For any whole number n greater than 2, odd or even, the even number $2n$ can be expressed as the sum of two prime numbers.

Now I would like to introduce two concepts that will be used in my article. They are **non prime** and **pair**. The non prime number is defined as the odd number which is not prime. It can be either 1 or an odd composite number.

Next, we define the concept of pairs. Two odd numbers o_1 and o_2 that are smaller than the even number $2n$ are pair to each other to be $2n$ if $o_1 + o_2 = 2n$. Similarly, they are pair to each other to be $2(n+1)$ if they are smaller than $2(n+1)$ and their sum is equal to that value.

The induction method [1] is used to prove this conjecture. The process of our proving is as follow:

- i) Prove that the conjecture is true for $n = 3$.
- ii) Assume that the conjecture is true for n , prove that the conjecture is true for $(n+1)$.

We do this by doing the fragmentation of the odd integers smaller than $2n$ into three main cases: total of prime is greater than total of non prime, total of prime is equal to total of non prime, and total of non prime is greater than total of prime. The reductio ad absurdum method [2] is used to prove that the false conjecture for $(n+1)$ will result in contradiction.

Finally, the Pigeonhole Principle [4] will be used for the last case of my proving

III. THE PROOF

First, the conjecture is true for $n = 3$ since $2n = 6 = 3 + 3$.

Now we assume that the conjecture is true for n , we begin to prove that it is also true for $(n+1)$. The following are the scenarios that can take place.

We define $T_p(n)$ and $T_n(n)$ as the total of prime numbers and non prime numbers smaller than $2n$, respectively

1) **Scenario 1:** $T_p(n) > T_n(n)$

Then from 1 to $2n$ there are n odd numbers, including m prime numbers and $(n - m)$ non-prime numbers with $m > (n - m)$.

a) $(2n+1)$ is prime.

From 1 to $2(n+1)$ there are $(n+1)$ odd numbers, including $(m+1)$ prime numbers and $(n - m)$ non-prime numbers, and of course $(m+1) > (n - m)$.

Let $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_{m+1}$ be the $(m+1)$ odd prime numbers mentioned above.

Subtraction of $2(n+1)$ with the prime numbers $(m+1)$ above will result in a series of odd numbers $o_1 = 2n - p_1, o_2 = 2n - p_2, \dots, o_{m+1} = 2n - p_{m+1}$. Among them, there are at most $(n-m)$ numbers that are non prime. The remaining numbers, in this case, must be prime. There are at least $(m+1) - (n-m) = (2m+1-n)$ of them. That means we have at least $(2m+1-n)$ odd prime numbers which are paired to each other internally to be $2(n+1)$. The conjecture has been proved for this scenario with $2(n+1)$.

This methodology will be reused for the next scenarios.

b) $(2n+1)$ is non prime

From 1 to $2(n+1)$ there are $(n+1)$ odd numbers, including m prime numbers and $(n - m + 1)$ non-prime numbers, Since

$m > (n - m)$, the case $m < (n - m + 1)$ cannot happen. So we have only two subcases here

- If $m > (n - m + 1)$, things will be the same as in a). Following the logic of the above section, we have at least $m - (n - m + 1)$ odd prime numbers that are paired to each other internally to be $2(n+1)$.

- If $m = (n - m + 1)$, at $2(n+1)$ the total of odd prime numbers is equal to the total of odd non prime ones. Since 1 and $(2n+1)$ are paired with each other to be $2(n+1)$, there is at most $(m-2)$ non prime numbers to pair with prime numbers to be $2(n+1)$. So we have at least 2 prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$. The conjecture has been proved for b).

2) **Scenario 2:** $T_p(n) = T_n(n)$

That means from 1 to $2n$ there are n odd numbers, including m prime numbers and $(n - m)$ non-prime numbers with $m = (n - m)$.

a) $(2n+1)$ is prime.

From 1 to $2(n+1)$ there are $(n+1)$ odd numbers, including $(m+1)$ prime numbers and $(n - m)$ non-prime numbers, and of course $(m+1) > (n - m)$. Applying a similar logic of subcase a) of case 1), we have the conclusion that there exist prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$ in this case. Even if all the $(n-m)$ non prime numbers are paired with prime numbers to be $2(n+1)$, we have at least 1 prime number pairs with itself to be $2(n+1)$. It is $(n+1)$.

b) $(2n+1)$ is non prime

From 1 to $2(n+1)$ there are $(n+1)$ odd numbers, including m prime numbers and $(n - m + 1)$ non-prime numbers.

Since 1 is paired with $(2n+1)$ to be $2(n+1)$, the remaining non prime numbers are $(n-m+1)-2 = (n-m-1)$, which is smaller than m .

Similarity, here we have the prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$ in this case. Even if all the $(n-m-1)$ non prime numbers are paired with prime numbers to be $2(n+1)$, we have at least 1 prime number to be paired with itself to be $2(n+1)$. It is $(n+1)$.

Before going to the next cases, I would like to say about the algorithm of adding 2 to be used in proving them.

Since the conjecture is true for $2n$, we have at least two prime numbers p_1 and p_2 smaller than $2n$ so that $p_1 + p_2 = 2n$. We also have $2(n+1) = 2n+2 = p_1 + (p_2 + 2) = p_2 + (p_1 + 2)$. If the conjecture is false for $2(n+1)$, both (p_1+2) and (p_2+2) must be non prime. This logic will be used throughout the remaining scenario to prove the conjecture.

3) **Scenario 3:** $T_p(n+1) < T_n(n+1)$

Again, let us say from 1 to $2n$ there are n odd numbers, including m prime numbers and $(n-m)$ non prime numbers with $m < (n - m)$. For that reason $(n - m) \geq (m + 1)$

When $(2n+1)$ is prime, then from 1 to $2(n+1)$ we have $(m+1)$ prime numbers and $(n-m)$ non prime numbers.

When $(2n+1)$ is non prime, then from 1 to $2(n+1)$ we have m prime numbers and $(n-m+1)$ non prime numbers.

We call the prime numbers which are paired with each other $2n$ as t with $0 \leq t \leq m$. We will calculate the other pairs based on t .

The total of prime numbers to be paired with non prime number to be $2n$ will be $(m-t)$. This is also the total of non prime number to be pair with prime numbers to be $2n$.

The total numbers of non prime numbers to be paired with each other to be $2n$ will be $(n-m) - (m-t) = (n+t-2m)$.

Assume that the conjecture is false for $2(n+1)$, each of t prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2n$ above must be non prime when adding 2. In addition, each of $(m-t)$ non prime numbers to pair with prime numbers to be $2n$ above must remain non prime when adding 2.

So the total of non prime - prime couples to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$ **until now** will be the sum of the two above results. They are $t + (m-t) = m$. In case $(2n+1)$ is prime, the pair $(1, 2n+1)$ adds 1 to this value, making it $(m+1)$.

This result matches with the fact that all prime numbers are pair with non prime numbers to be $2(n+1)$. That means there must be no more pairs of prime - non prime to be found at $2(n+1)$.

Now we analyze the next two groups of pairs. The first group is created when all $(m-t)$ of prime numbers to pair with non prime numbers to be $2n$ are added with 2. The second one is the result when we add 2 to all $(n-m) - (m-t)$ non prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2n$. The combination of these two groups results in $(m-t) + (n-m) - (m-t) = (n-m)$ pairs. They include the mixture of prime - non prime pairs, which are duplicated with some or all of the ones created by adding 2 to the numbers in the first two groups, and non prime - non prime pairs to be $2(n+1)$

Now we have two sub cases here

a) The $(n-m)$ pairs above are not all pairs of odd numbers that sum up to $2(n+1)$

- If $(n+1)$ is an even number, we have the total of pairs where components are the odd numbers so that their sums are equal to $2(n+1)$ is $(n+1)/2$. Since $(n-m)$ pairs above are not all of these $(n+1)/2$ pairs, we have $(n - m) < (n + 1)/2 \Rightarrow 2(n - m) < (n + 1) \Rightarrow 2n - 2m < (n + 1) \Rightarrow (n - m) < (m + 1)$. This result contradicts our assumption. So the fact that the conjecture is not true for this case is not correct. That means that the conjecture must be true for this case.

- If $(n+1)$ is an odd number, we have the total of pairs where components are the odd numbers so that their sum is equal to $2(n+1)$ is $(n+2)/2$. Since $(n-m)$ pairs above are not all of these $(n+2)/2$ pairs, we have $(n - m) < (n + 2)/2 \Rightarrow 2(n - m) < (n + 2) \Rightarrow 2n - 2m < (n + 2) \Rightarrow (n - m) < (m + 2)$.

Combined with our assumption $(n - m) \geq (m + 1)$, we have $(m + 1) \leq (n - m) < (m + 2) \Rightarrow (n-m) = (m+1)$.

When $(2n+1)$ is prime, from 1 to $2(n+1)$ we have $(m+1)$ odd prime numbers and $(n-m)$ odd non prime numbers. In this case they are equal to each other.

Since $(n+1)$ is an odd number, we can express it in the form $(n+1) = kp$ where k is an odd number and p is an odd prime number. So $2(n+1) = 2kp$.

If $k = 1$ we have $2(n+1) = 2p = p + p$. The conjecture is true for this case.

If $k > 1$ ($k = 3, 5, 7$ etc.) we have $2(n+1) = kp + kp$ or $2(n+1) = (k-2)p + (k+2)p$. if k is big enough, we can have

$2(n+1) = (k-4)p + (k+4)p$ or $(k-6)p + (k+6)p$ etc. This means that we have at least two pairs of non prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$. Since the total of odd prime numbers is equal to the total of odd non prime numbers, we use the same methodology as in Scenario 2 to reach the conclusion that there exist prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$.

A special case occurs with $k = 3$. Here we have $2(n+1) = 3p + 3p$. The conjecture is true for $p = 3$ and $p = 5$, which results in $2(n+1) = 18$ and 30 . So we consider the case p is greater than 5 . So we also have $2(n+1) = k(p-2) + k(p+2)$ or $k(p-4) + k(p+4)$ etc. We also reach the same conclusion that there are at least two pairs of non prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$, which results in the fact that there exist prime numbers to pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$.

When $2(n+1)$ is non prime, this means that from 1 to $2(n+1)$ the total of odd prime numbers is m and the total of odd non prime numbers is $(n-m+1) = (m+1) + 1 = m+2$. We have 2 non prime numbers to be pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$. They are 1 and $(2n+1)$. Using the same analysis method with equation $2(n+1) = 2kp$ for the case $2(n+1)$ is prime, we have at least 2 other pairs of non prime - non prime to be pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$ besides the pair 1 and $(2n+1)$ mentioned above, which results in the same conclusion.

In summary, the conjecture has been proved as true for sub case a) when the $(n-m)$ pairs created from adding 2 for the last two groups above are not all the pairs of odd numbers that sum up to $2(n+1)$ no matter $(n+1)$ is odd or even.

b) The $(n-m)$ pairs above cover all the pairs of odd numbers that sum to $2(n+1)$.

b1) If $(n+1)$ is an odd number, we have the total of pairs where the components are odd numbers so that their sum is equal to $2(n+1)$ is $(n+2)/2$ and $(n-m) = (n+2)/2 \Rightarrow 2(n-m) = (n+2) \Rightarrow 2n - 2m = (n+2) \Rightarrow (n-m) = (m+2) = (m+1) + 1$.

So when the conjecture is false for this case, we have two sub cases:

If $2(n+1)$ is prime, among $(n-m)$ pairs of odd numbers which are paired with each other to be $2(n+1)$, we have $(m+1)$ pairs of prime - non prime and 1 pair of non prime - non prime.

Since $(n+1)$ is an odd number, it can be expressed in the format $(n+1) = kp$ with k is an odd number and p is a prime number. Then we have $2(n+1) = 2kp = kp + kp$.

If $k = 1$ we have $2(n+1) = p + p$, The conjecture is true for this case.

If $k > 3$, ($k = 5, 7, 9$ etc.) $kp + kp$ is the pair of non prime - non prime above. However, $2(n+1)$ can also be expressed as $(k-2)p + (k+2)p$. That means we have at least two more non prime - non prime pairs, which contradicts the above conclusion that only one pair of this type exists. So the conjecture must be true here.

A special case occurs with $k = 3$. Here we have $2(n+1) = 3p + 3p$. The conjecture is true for $p = 3$ and $p = 5$, which results in $2(n+1) = 18$ and 30 . So we consider the case p is greater than 5 . So we also have $2(n+1) = k(p-2) + k(p+2)$. We reach the same conclusion that there are more than 1 pair of non

prime numbers to be pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$ which results in the same conclusion as above. If $2(n+1)$ is non prime, among $(n-m)$ pairs of odd numbers which are paired with each other to be $2(n+1)$, we have m pair of prime - non prime and 2 pair of non prime - non prime. One of them is the pair of 1 and $(2n+1)$. Using the same analysis method with equation $2(n+1) = 2kp$ for the case $2(n+1)$ is prime, we have at least 2 other pairs of non prime - non prime to be pair with each other to be $2(n+1)$ besides the pair 1 and $(2n+1)$ mentioned above, which results in the same conclusion.

In conclusion, the conjecture is true for b1) with $(n+1)$ is an odd number.

b2) If $(n+1)$ is an even number, we have the total of pairs where the components are odd numbers so that their sum is equal to $2(n+1)$ is $(n+1)/2$ and $(n-m) = (n+1)/2 \Rightarrow 2(n-m) = (n+1) \Rightarrow 2n - 2m = (n+1) \Rightarrow (n-m) = (m+1)$

That means $2(n+1) = 4(m+1)$.

Now we begin to apply the **Pigeon Principle** for this sub case

The Pigeon Principle (PHP) [4] says:

If n items (pigeons) are placed into k containers (pigeon-holes) and $n > k$, then at least one container contains more than one item.

* If $2(n+1)$ is prime, from 1 to $4(m+1)$ there are $2(m+1)$ odd numbers including $(m+1)$ odd prime numbers and $(m+1)$ odd non prime numbers.

Let $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_{m+1}$ be the $(m+1)$ odd prime numbers mentioned above. We set distinct unordered pairs $(p_1, p_2), (p_1, p_3), \dots, (p_m, p_{m+1})$.

Since the number of unordered pairs above (p_i, p_j) allows repetition (i.e $p_i = p_j$ is allowed) we have the total of these pairs is equal to

$$\frac{(m+1)!}{2!(m-1)!} + (m+1) = \frac{(m+1)(m+2)}{2}$$

Next, we calculate the total possible values for the sum $S = (p_i + p_j)$.

Since the smallest odd prime number is 3 , we have that the smallest possible sum is $\min(p_i + p_j) = 3 + 3 = 6$.

Similarly, the largest odd prime number is $2(n+1) = (4m+3)$. So, the largest possible sum is $\max(p_i + p_j) = (4m+3) + (4m+3) = 8m+6$.

We want to count the number of even integers in: $[6, (8m+6)]$, spaced by 2 .

Using the formula for the number of terms in an arithmetic sequence:

$$\# \text{terms} = \frac{\text{Last} - \text{First}}{\text{Step}} + 1$$

we find that the number of even integers is $[(8m+6) - 6]/2 + 1 = (4m + 1)$.

Obviously $4m > 2 \Rightarrow (4(m+1)) > 6$

Also, we have $(8m + 6) > 4(m+1)$

By this calculation, we find that $4(m+1)$ lies within the interval $[6, (8m+6)]$.

Now we have to prove that $(m+1)(m+2)/2 > 4m + 1$

We calculate the expression $(m+1)(m+2) - 2(4m+1) = m^2 + 3m + 2 - 8m - 2 = m^2 - 5m = m(m-5)$

Since m must be greater than 5 (With $m \leq 5$ we have the even number $4(m+1)$ that matches the Goldbach conjecture), we have $(m+1)(m+2)/2 > (4m+1)$.

The number of sums (the total of pairs) is considered the pigeons, and the total of possible value is considered the pigeonholes. More sums than possible values result in the fact that at least one sum value must occur more than once. It forces overlapping: some even number must appear multiple times.

In addition, we see that $4(m+1)$ is within the interval $[6, (8m+6)]$. We reach the conclusion that $4(m+1)$ must be hit by at least one pair $(p_i + p_j) = 4(m+1)$

* If $(2n+1)$ is non prime, from 1 to $4(m+1)$ there are $2(m+1)$ odd numbers including m odd prime numbers and $(m+2)$ odd non prime numbers.

Let $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_m$ be the m odd prime numbers mentioned above. We setup distinct unordered pairs $(p_1, p_2), (p_1, p_3), \dots, (p_{m-1}, p_m)$.

Since the number of unordered pairs above (p_i, p_j) allows repetition (i.e $p_i = p_j$ is allowed) we have that the total of these pairs is equal to

$$\frac{m!}{2!(m-2)!} + m = \frac{m(m+1)}{2}$$

Next, we calculate the total possible values for the sum $S = (p_i + p_j)$.

Since the smallest odd prime number is 3, we have that the smallest possible sum is $\min(p_i + p_j) = 3 + 3 = 6$.

Similarly, the largest odd prime number is $(2n-1) = (4m+1)$. So, the largest possible sum is $\max(p_i + p_j) = (4m+1) + (4m+1) = 8m+2$.

We want to count the number of even integers in: $[6, (8m+2)]$, spaced by 2.

Using the formula for the number of terms in an arithmetic sequence:

$$\#terms = \frac{Last - First}{Step} + 1$$

we have the number of even integers is $[(8m+2) - 6]/2 + 1 = (4m - 1)$.

Obviously $4m > 2 \Rightarrow (4(m+1)) > 6$

Also, we have $(8m+2) > 4(m+1)$

By this calculation, We find that $4(m+1)$ lies within the interval $[6, (8m+2)]$.

Now we have to prove that $m(m+1)/2 > (4m-1)$

We calculate the expression $m(m+1) - 2(4m-1) = m^2 + m - 8m + 2 = m^2 - 7m + 2 = (m-1)(m-6) + 4$.

Since m must be greater than 6 (With $m \leq 6$ we have the even number $4(m+1)$ matches the Goldbach conjecture), we have $(m-1)(m-6) > 4 \Rightarrow m(m+1)/2 > (4m-1)$

The number of sums (the total of pairs) is considered the pigeons, and the total of possible values is considered the pigeonholes. More sums than possible values result in the fact that at least one sum value must occur more than once. It forces overlapping: some even number must appear multiple times.

In addition, we see that $4(m+1)$ is within the interval $[6, (8m+2)]$. We reach the conclusion that $4(m+1)$ must be hit by at least one pair $(p_i + p_j) = 4(m+1)$

With these two scenarios, we have that the Goldbach conjecture is true for the case $(n+1)$ is even.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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